

THE EFFECT OF TOUGHENED BMI MATRIX ON THE MECHANICAL PERFORMANCE OF CARBON FIBER COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we discuss the effect of toughened Bismaleimide (BMI) resin system on the mechanical performance of carbon fiber composites by various tests.

INTRODUCTION

At early stage of using advanced composites, investigation emphasis of composites focused on enhancing property of reinforcement agent, while neglected improving resin property.

In recent years, the most successful work on resin system may be the substitute bismaleimide for epoxy in advance composites. The state-of-art epoxy resin such as TGMDA has been as matrix generally used in high performance composites. However, epoxy resin typically exhibit poor strength at elevated temperature after aging in humidity environments, more than all, the fracture toughness, its strain of fracture appear rather low.

It is well known that allowable strain design is one of design method based on the strain. The toughness of resin as matrix of fiber composite is one of important factors for determining allowable strain value. The more toughness of resin, the higher strain value. It is also for brittle material, rather low allowable strain should be determined for safety consideration. So material utilization would be very low. Consequently, many high toughness resin systems have been developing. As to general epoxy resin, higher toughness was usually obtained by sacrificing thermal resistance. Though some resins have higher toughness, they can not be used either because of their weak thermal property.

The BMI resin system has excellent F.S.T.(Fire, Smoke and Toxic gas emission) performance. It is a good fire retardant candidate materials. However, like other thermoset resin, BMI resin has also exhibited its brittleness. BMI toughened can be obtained by several chemical approaches. Prof. Varma discussed the toughness effect on BMI system by addition of elastomer¹. Dr. Stenzenberger introduced a co-polymerisation of allylbenzene derivative with BMI². Ciba-geigy co. recommended a o,o' diallylbisphenol system³. We use a kind of alkene compound reaction with BMI to improve toughness. We call this system after QY8911. About generally properties of QY8911 have published some papers⁴⁻⁵. In this paper, we will concentratively discuss about toughened mechanical properties of BMI composites.

1. Target of toughened BMI

In generally speaking several different levels of BMI toughness can be

get by using different methods. But in composites, resin should be match with reinforcing fiber. At present, only a kind of medium strain level carbon fiber can be get, its elongation is about from 1.3% to 1.5%. With the resin matched, its elongation should be about 2.2%. According to strain level mentioned above, we designed a formulation for BMI resin system. QY8911 resin reported in this paper was modified of commercially available BMI.

The neat resin properties of QY8911 are listed in table I.

2. Experiment

(1). Carbon fiber

T300-3000-40B carbon fiber was used, its main properties achieved by testing are shown in table II.

(2). Preparing samples

Samples for testing were laid up with prepreg by hands. After finishing bagging procedures, laminates were cured in an autoclave. The schedule is as follows: Curing at 177°C under 0.5 Mpa pressure for 2 hours, then the samples moved into an oven for post curing at 200-210°C for 3 hours. For inspecting quality of the samples, all laminates were evaluated by C-scanning and X-ray display. C-scanning can show different colour that represent different quality level. Some parts of samples were investigated by metallograph and electronic microscope.

(3). Testing items concerning with toughness of composites

Eight configurations of samples were prepared.

- a. 0° orientation laminates for determining compression strength.
- b. 90° orientation laminates for determining transverse tensile strength, ultimate strain and flexure property.
- c. [$\pm 252/90$]_s orientation laminates for measuring the knee point strength at edge delamination.
- d. [$\pm 302/90/90$]_s orientation laminates for measuring the knee point strain at edge delamination.
- e. 56 plies 0° orientation laminates with end notch was done to flexure test in searching of interlaminar fracture G_{Ic} .
- f. [$\pm 45/0/90$]_{2s} laminates with 6.3mm open hole in 230x38x1.8 mm specimen size for testing tension strength.
- g. [$\pm 45/0/90$]_{2s} laminates in 60x90 mm size for testing compression after impact.
- h. 80 plies $\pm 45^\circ$ and 83 plies 0° orientation laminates with one notch at each side unsymmetrically (see Fig.1) for testing compression interlaminar shear.

(4) Results

a. 0° Compression strength test

The compression test as specified in standard was employed to characterize the longitudinal compression.

Data are shown in table III that represent the laminate with the toughened matrix having excellent compression strength at room temperature and higher temperature.

b. 90° transverse tensile strength and its ultimate strain

90° tensile strength and its ultimate strain are usually used to evaluate the toughness of matrix resin. The datum is shown in table III.

c. [$\pm 252/90$]_s edge delamination strength

This test was employed to give a measure of the interlaminated fracture toughness. The lay up utilized [$\pm 252/90$]_s gave a measure of the mixed mode fracture toughness G_{Ic} , crack opening, and G_{IIc} shear of critical importance in this test is the strength of the resin/fiber interface. The result is also shown in table III. Fig.2 shows the strain-stress curve during the edge delamination tension test.

d. 90° tensile and flexure strength

90° tensile strength and ultimate strain were mainly depended on resin property. During 90° flexure testing, the failure may occur in the matrix or at the fiber/matrix interface. Assuming that the failure occurs in the matrix, this test yields datum which would be related to toughness of the resin. The result were also listed in table III.

e. [$\pm 30_2/90/90$]_s delamination strain

The size of sample is 254x38x1.3 mm. After recording of strain at initial delamination, the fracture toughness G_c is calculated, with the results listed in Table IV Fig.3 shows delamination occurred in the laminate under static tension.

f. Stress analysis of the end notch flexure (ENF) specimen for mode II delamination of composite materials.

The specimen likes a beam suffered a three point bending, at one end of specimen a midplane starter crack of desired length introduced. A mode II critical strain energy release rate G_{IIc} , is determined from the ENF test by observing the load and the deflection associated with the onset of crack growth.⁶ The result is shown in Table V.

g. Open-hole tension strength and strain

The open-hole test specimens were loaded to failure. In most case fracture originated at the edge of the hole and propagated perpendicular to the loading at the edge of the hole and subsequently followed by the fracture of internal plies prior to complete separation of the laminate. The QY8911/T300 exhibited the strength of 344.5 Mpa and strain of 5154 micro strain.

h. Compression interlaminar shear

The data represent a combination property of shear and compression. The results are also listed in Table III.

i. compressure after impact

Each specimen was suffered a certain impact, and then it was removed to fixture for compression test. Relation of damage area and residual compressure load are listed in Table IV.

(5) Analysis

a. As mentioned above, the more toughness, the lower thermal resistance for thermoset resin type composite. Table V compare QY8911/T300 composite with novlac epoxy/T300 composite. Novlac resin system have been using since 1969 in carbon composite in China.⁷ The data are shown, although the thermal properties of modified BMI are not high, they still can meet the requirement of aircraft structure.

b. Edge delamination fracture test is based on the fact that the delamination usually appear in free edge when laid up at ± 25 or ± 30 orientation. The test specimen is delaminated as a mixture of Mode I (interlaminar tension or peel) and Mode II (interlaminar shear). The critical value of G_c at delamination onset is a measure of the interlaminar fracture toughness of the composite. So edge delamination tension is a simple test for measuring the interlaminar fracture toughness of fiber composite.

3. CONCLUSION

(1). With primary test data, we can see, modified BMI QY8911 have higher toughness level than other some modified BMI resin systems.

(2). Although the thermal resistance of QY8911 resin system decrease slightly, it is still satisfied with the requirements of composite materials used for the aircraft.

(3). Modified BMI resin system QY8911 has many other advantages such as excellent handleability, good tack and drap over one month shelf-life at ambient temperature and low sensitivity to pressure.

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Table I. QY8911 neat resin properties

Tensile strength	65.6	Mpa
Tensile modulus	3.05	Gpa
Elongation at failure	2.2	%

Table II. Properties of T300 Carbon Fiber

Tensile strength	1627.5	Mpa
Tensile modulus	126.9	Gpa
Elongation at failure	1.49	%

Table III. Properties of modified BMI QY8911 / T300

Compression strength 25°C	1527	Mpa
150°C	1266	Mpa
90° tensile strength	66	Mpa
90° tensile ultimate strain	6865	
Edge delamination initial Strength [$\pm 25_2/90$] _s	210.2	Mpa
90° flexure strength (span ratio 32)	105.3	Mpa
90° flexure strength (span ratio 16)	114.5	Mpa
Initial delamination strain	0.00476	mm
Fracture toughness Gc [$\pm 30_2/90/90$] _s	0.2212	Mpa-mm
ENF, G _{11c}	497 ± 52	J/M ²
Open-hole strength	344.5	Mpa
Open-hole ultimate strain	5154	$\mu\epsilon$
Compression interlaminar shear [$\pm 45_0$]	53	Mpa
Compression interlaminar Shear [0°]	88	Mpa

Table IV. Residual compressure strength after impact

Damage area (mm)	Residual compressure load	
0	35	KN
15 x 15	34	KN
20 x 20	30	KN
25 x 25	26	KN
30 x 30	26	KN
35 x 35	25	KN

Table V.

Item	T ^o c	QY8911/T300	Novlac/T300
Flexure strength (Mpa)	25	1915.1	1650.1
	100		1166.2
	120	1759.3	
	150	1591.4	
	180	1458.2	
	200	1352.2	
Short beam shear (Mpa)	25	104.5	67.6
	100		56.0
	120	80.1	
	150	72.9	
	200	59.4	